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E³UDRES² common R&I agenda and action plan | Date 30-Sep-2025

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the E³UDRES² common research and innovation agenda (chapter 1) and the action plan (chapter 2) for implementing the agenda. It summarizes the core results elaborated in the work packages directed to the research agenda, research infrastructure, human resource, open science and outreach.

This research agenda was developed within the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project (Nr.101071317) with the six E³UDRES² founding partners as members of the consortium. The new E³UDRES² partners were integrated as participants in surveys, interviews and focus groups as well as in the External Expert Advisory Board.

The common research and innovation agenda (chapter 1) was adopted by all decision-making bodies within the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators consortium:

- **IPS:** The document was approved by IPS on July 28th 2025.
- **ViA:** The document was approved by the ViA senate on August 27th 2025.
- **STPUAS:** The Extended University Leadership thoroughly discussed the document during its meeting on June 11th 2025 and welcomed its approach, objectives, scope and content.
- **UPT:** The document was approved by UPT on September 4th 2025
- **UCLL:** The document was approved by the management of UCLL on August 22nd 2025.
- **MATE:** After an (1) initial check by the International Directorate and a (2) legal review by the Legal Department, the agenda and the approval text were sent to the Rectorate Office of MATE. (3) After a final review by the Office, the rector (as the legal representative of the university) signed the approval on 27th August 2025.

The Executive Board of the E³UDRES² Alliance, including those partners who were not full partners in the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, was also actively informed during its meeting on June 13th 2025 about objectives and scope of this document.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

CoARA – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

E³UDRES² – Engaged European Entrepreneurial University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

ECSA – European Citizen Science Association

EEAB – External Expert Advisory Board

EIT – European Institute of Innovation & Technology

EOSC – European Open Science Cloud

EU – European Union

HR – Human Resources

HRS4R – Human Resources Strategi for Research

IoT – Internet of Things

MSCA – Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

NGO – Non-Governmental Organization

OA – Open Access

OASPA – Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association

OE – Open Education

OER – Open Education Repository

OI – Open Innovation

OpenAIRE – Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe

OS – Open Science

OSF – Open Science Framework

OTM-R – Open Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment of Researchers

RDM – Research Data Management

SME – Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

WP – Work Package

ZENODO – EU Open Research Repository

Executive Summary

This research and innovation agenda (chapter 1) represents the core outcome of work package 2 of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project. It summarizes the main strategic pillars which were jointly developed with all work packages within the project.

The agenda was developed by the project partners of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, which represent the six founding partners of the E³UDRES² European University Alliance. During the project phase of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, the E³UDRES² European University Alliance was expanded by three new partners. Those three partners were involved in the development process of the agenda by contributing as External Expert Advisory Board members, and were also invited to participate in survey, focus groups and interviews.

To confirm the commitment of the E³UDRES² European University Alliance to sustainably implement this agenda, all E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators partners have approved the agenda by their internal decision-making bodies. In addition to that, the E³UDRES² Executive Board was informed about the agenda.

The joint research and innovation agenda follows the principle of impact driven research and innovation as driver for smart and sustainable regions. It aims to develop European solutions for regional challenges. To achieve this goal, a diverse and trustful ecosystem is necessary.

As European University, E³UDRES² will contribute to the further development of the European Research Area.

The following key pillars of the joint research and innovation agenda were identified:

- future oriented agenda;
- sharing research infrastructure;
- open education, open science and open innovation;
- engaging citizens and society;
- human resources;
- research and innovation ecosystems.

The research and innovation agenda states the commitment of the E³UDRES² alliance to follow European and international standards regarding open science and human resources in research and actively contributes to the development of alternative research assessment methods.

Participation in European networks is a relevant component for an impactful research environment.

This document summarizes the main pillars of the joint E³UDRES² research and innovation agenda. All pillars are supported by more detailed guidelines, recommendations and actions plans. The document does not claim to describe every detail that is necessary for the implementation of the research and innovation agenda.

The action plan (chapter 2) represents the steps to sustainably implement the common research and innovation in the research and innovation activities of the E³UDRES² alliance and its partners.

1. Common Research and Innovation Agenda

1.1 Vision & Mission: European Solutions for Regional Challenges

The European University E³UDRES² (<https://eudres.eu/>) commits itself to a human-centered and challenge-based approach in education, research and innovation with a special focus on the further development of European Smart and Sustainable Regions. E³UDRES² unites nine higher education institutions from all over Europe, including more than thirty-five associated partners from the business, science and education sectors.

European University Alliances are motors to advance the European Higher Education Landscape as well as expertise hubs to drive forward research excellence and innovation for and to the European regions. European University Alliances are more than just networks—they combine resources, expertise, and partnerships that extend far beyond traditional collaborations. With this necessary power the E³UDRES² Alliance has the aim to develop future oriented solutions for smart and sustainable regions, Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Map of E³UDRES² Alliance

The E³UDRES² Alliance upholds European values (human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, rule of law, Human rights) with its research activities, regardless of geopolitical developments worldwide. We strengthen our European Identity by collaborating in education, research and innovation. Together, we make an impact on European Research and Innovation Capacity and to a strong Europe which will face upcoming challenges.

Research and Innovation Agenda

This research and innovation agenda further advances the E³UDRES² European University Alliance, positioning it as a key driver of innovative solutions to regional challenges.

The core values of research and innovation within the E³UDRES² alliance are:

- **Academic integrity:**
With our commitment to scientific integrity, we are dedicated to maintaining high academic standards in knowledge generation, transfer and innovation. Our employees not only apply these standards but also create awareness among students to further develop the academic culture.
- **Research freedom:**
The freedom of science is a valuable asset that contributes to the further development and protection of our society, our economy and our ecosystem without having to respond to unjustified external interference.
- **Transparency:**
Transparency in decision-making is a key element in creating a trusting environment for co-creation and bottom-up processes.
- **Openness:**
Whenever possible from the legal perspective, the results of R&I activities from the E³UDRES² Alliance are made available to the scientific community, to cooperation partners and stakeholders, to citizens and society for further valorisation to generate greater impact. At the same time, citizens, stakeholders, partners, industry and society are important input-givers and co-creators in the whole R&I process, all contributing to an open science and innovation ecosystem.
- **Supportive working conditions:**
We are focusing on people and talents. The E³UDRES² Alliance is an attractive place to work and study. With supportive working and training conditions, we put people at the centre of everything we do, thereby promoting personal growth, equality, equity, diversity and inclusion, as embedded in the frameworks of the European Higher Education Area and of the European Research Area.

The following joint Research and Innovation Agenda specifically addresses the following topics:

- Future Oriented Agenda
- Sharing Research Infrastructure
- Open Science, Innovation, Education
- Engaging Citizens and Society
- Human Resources
- Research and Innovation Ecosystem

1.2 Future Oriented Agenda

Policy:

The E³UDRES² European University Alliance is a driver of innovation with and for smart and sustainable regions, collaborating with a variety of stakeholders and promoting European values.

Since its establishment in 2020, the E³UDRES² alliance has identified core topics and focus areas based on the interdisciplinary expertise of its partners and the needs of the regions. In 2023, based on the already existing Research Networks and in the scope of the prolongation of the E³UDRES² alliance to phase 2, the following four focus areas were defined:

1. Health, Wellbeing and Social Inclusion for Regions
2. Digital Solutions and (Applied) Deep Tech for Regions
3. Resilient Economy and Innovation for Regions
4. Creative Industries for Region's Identity

These core topics are included in the future oriented agenda. From an overarching perspective, as promoter of European values, the E³UDRES² alliance always includes the aspects of securing and advancing democracy, overcoming of social inequalities and promoting environmental sustainability in all its research and innovation activities.

Support and Infrastructure:

The development of infrastructures such as (digital) platforms which support the sharing of knowledge, networking and the co-creation process, is crucial to support the success of the E³UDRES² research and innovation agenda. In this scope, it is very important to keep focussing on the development of the joint E³UDRES² platform "E³UDRES² Arena," including the bank of researchers as database of expertise. Involving citizens through participatory formats and citizen science initiatives further strengthens this ecosystem by integrating diverse perspectives and real-world relevance.

Incentive mechanisms such as conferences, innovation calls and awards of excellence help develop new creative, interdisciplinary ideas and approaches for research and innovation inside the alliance and with its partners and stakeholders.

Joint research support units, to be drafted and installed in the broader alliance context, will support researchers and innovators to identify potential calls for their innovative ideas to develop targeted funding applications and expand their cooperation networks.

Training, like e.g. proposal writing, project management etc. accompany the personal growth of the individual actors in the research process to succeed in competitive award procedures and are progressively included in more comprehensive training programmes and joint activities.

Networking events ensure broader collaboration. These gatherings help expand the pool of engaged individuals inside and outside the partner institutions by creating more points of contact and fostering familiarity among a wider range of contributors. Since people tend to collaborate with those they know, increasing the number of personal connections is key to involving more individuals and boosting the overall capacity of the project.

E³UDRES² is in high competition with other national and international research players, whereas the core funding of E³UDRES² research and innovation activities needs to be generated by successful research proposals. The European Research Area with its funding opportunities is a high priority for the E³UDRES² research activities, not only focusing on the (future) Research Framework Programmes but also exploiting other funding schemes, e.g. from the EIT or MSCA.

Governance:

Each Focus Area will have a leading team to promote the further collaboration and setting up of research networks and Centres of Excellence.

The E³UDRES² Scientific Councils, already established in the E³UDRES² alliance acts as expert group for promoting excellence in research and further development of the E³UDRES² research activities and strategy.

Collaboration and partnerships:

E³UDRES² strongly promotes the collaboration with regional stakeholders from different countries and fields e.g. NGOs, companies, industries, civil society, citizens, start-ups, policy makers etc. It maintains a diverse network of associated partners including higher education institutions from other European and potentially non-European countries, regional development agencies and networks.

Regional and open innovation hubs, which are developed in other E³UDRES²-related activities serve as bridges for new partnerships and further collaboration with the regions.

E³UDRES² will strengthen the involvement of partners from Ukraine and Western Balkans by ensuring access to funding, through facilitation of joint research collaborations, involvement in mobility and knowledge exchange programs, offering mentoring and career development support, ensuring access to training and funding opportunities, promoting participation in Centres of Excellence.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

We regularly monitor the relevance of our activities and our impact to the regions by involving external stakeholders (e.g. External Advisory Board, E³UDRES² Scientific Board, Regional communities, and others)

We commit to actively contribute to CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) and to successively implement new ways of research assessment.

We recognise the principles of CoARA¹ and identified the most urgent ones for our alliance:

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
3. Engage resources to reform research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to
4. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes
5. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition
6. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

¹ CoARA, retrieved on 28 May 2025 from <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>

1.3 Sharing Research Infrastructure

Policy:

The E³UDRES² alliance highly benefits from pooling resources and sharing research infrastructure that contribute to enabling innovation, cross-disciplinarity, applied science, citizen science and open science:

- *Cross-disciplinarity*: ambassadors within shared spaces to encourage collaborative innovation.
- *Citizen science and community building*: involving local communities in utilizing infrastructures for participatory innovation in areas like sustainability and healthcare.
- *Digital technologies and open science principles*: shared data repositories, AI analytics, and cloud computing to enhance innovation and increase added value.

E³UDRES² is unique due to its interdisciplinary orientation and the diversity of its expertise and resources, as well as its anchoring in the regions. By opening up the research infrastructure within the alliance, existing resources can be utilised more efficiently. When acquiring new relevant research infrastructure, the possible joint utilisation within the alliance shall be considered, also in the context of innovation activities when legally possible.

Therefore, all E³UDRES² partners agree to open their research infrastructure to the other E³UDRES² partners according to the following criteria:

- infrastructure has open resources.
- the user of the infrastructure gets training on the infrastructure or are supported by the “home institutions”.
- no legal regulation at the national or international level precludes making the infrastructure available to other partners.
- virtual availability shall be investigated wherever possible, to expand the target group of potential users from other institutions of the alliance.

Support and Infrastructure:

A database collects and makes visible information and responsibilities about the available research infrastructure which can be provided / shared from one partner to the other members of the alliance.

Technologies that could be shared for enabling and accelerating innovative research and development projects include:

- *Data and knowledge sharing platforms*: centralized R&I databases to facilitate seamless sharing of research findings, data, and resources.
- *Digital tools for collaboration*: cloud computing, collaborative platforms, and AI-based tools to streamline workflows and enhance efficiency.
- *Research-specific technologies*: IoT for environmental monitoring, telemedicine platforms for healthcare, and machine learning for societal trend analysis.

- *Open science support*: digital repositories and tools to support transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility in research, refined RDM and ethics.

The correct use of shared infrastructure can only be ensured by acquiring the necessary competences for each infrastructure. This is to be ensured through a skills roadmap and a targeted training programme. E³UDRES² and its partners act as peer-learning innovation hubs, offering hands-on learning and collaboration opportunities by sharing infrastructure.

Governance:

To enable an efficient and fruitful use of shared infrastructure, the following principles shall be followed:

- **Resource allocation**: balancing access and usage across institutions and disciplines.
- **Interoperability**: ensuring compatibility between diverse systems and technologies.
- **Sustainability**: addressing financial and environmental costs of maintaining shared infrastructures.
- **Governance and policy alignment**: having a clear governance model with policies that harmonize the trans-institutional priorities.

A robust resource management framework and standardized interoperability protocols are needed in form of guidelines and policies. Effective funding models shall be set to support long-term sustainability of shared infrastructure and collaboration. External funding such as grants and usage-based fees (on long term) shall be considered not to overburden any single institution.

Collaboration and partnerships:

We closely collaborate with each other based on our expertise and our focal points. Besides sharing infrastructure within the alliance we aim to expand the access to infrastructure owned or hosted by external partners (e.g. associated partners, research centres, etc.). In addition, we promote the collaboration with networks and initiatives (e.g. Makerspaces, technology hubs, etc.) to gain access to further infrastructure.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

Regular evaluations based on the resource management framework shall monitor the effectiveness of the joint use of infrastructure.

1.4 Open Science, Innovation, Education

Policy:

We promote open practices in education, research and innovation.

Open practices shall be embedded in policies and strategies at the E3UDRES2 alliance, that support culture change towards open science, open innovation and open education practices. Open access to the research outputs, data sharing, and the use of open educational resources and practices shall be mandated, while respecting each organization's autonomy. Open practices should value activities associated with openness (training, awareness raising, priority setting partnerships, outreach), and the inclusion of stakeholders in the research process, from defining priority research questions to knowledge translation and implementation (e.g. in community projects).

Our support for Open Innovation provides the consortium collaboration opportunities, clearer policy formation, and strategic plans, while a unified approach can boost funding, enhance institutional reputation, and align education with market needs; OI Hubs, shared platforms and co-creation labs further facilitate international collaboration and multidisciplinary interactions.

We work towards a full implementation of the following guiding principles for OS/OI/OE/OA in E³UDRES²:

- Accessibility – Ensure knowledge is openly accessible to all members of the Alliance.
- Transparency – Promote open methodologies & practices, peer review, and data sharing.
- Collaboration – Encourage interdisciplinary and global cooperation.
- Equity & Inclusion – Support diverse participation and multilingual resources.
- Sustainability – Ensure long-term open access and repository maintenance.

Support and Infrastructure:

To achieve openness, E³UDRES²:

- *invests in robust infrastructure and training:* Allocate resources to build and maintain digital repositories, collaborative platforms, and data management systems at the level of the alliance, while providing comprehensive training programs that equip researchers, educators, and students with the necessary skills to adopt open practices.
- *Raises awareness, incentivizes and rewards Open Practices:* Creates recognition and reward mechanisms such as funding opportunities, career advancement criteria, and awards that acknowledge contributions to open science, open innovation, and open education, encouraging broader adoption and sustained commitment to these practices in the E3UDRES2 alliance, but also foretake models in partner universities.
- *Digital tools and platforms:* Developing digital tools and platforms at E3UDRES2 for open practicing collaborative research and education.

The OS/OI/OE/OA strategy for the E³UDRES² alliance will consider the following topics:

- Training offers and incentives for Open Science skills and education (e.g. through Summer Schools);
- Open access to data, publications and enabling infrastructures (possibly third-party);
- Open Publishing practices and institutional policies and mechanisms to offer Open Science – including incentives and rewards where needed;
- Interconnection of partners' innovation & technology transfer structures in order to increase innovation visibility;
- Implementation of a system enabling partner institutions to detect connections among people, publications, opportunities in the context of Open Publishing.

Governance:

A joint E³UDRES² policy on OE/OA/OS/OI will set our priorities to support openness within the alliance.

The establishment of an Open Science and Open Education (or a joint OE/OA/OS/OI) Committee will guide the implementation and the further development of the open principles and will act as a monitoring instance.

Collaboration and partnerships:

Promote collaborative networks and partnerships: Establish and nurture partnerships of E³UDRES² with EOSC, national and international research consortia, industry, and governmental organizations to share best practices, pool resources, and drive innovation.

- Joint initiatives for OE/OA/OS/OI development;
- Horizon Europe projects as well as projects in other European grant schemes (e.g. EIT);
- Joint use of open data clouds;
- Joint DOI assignment;
- Open Education Repository (OER);
- Joint participation shall be supported in: EOSC, CoARA, ZENODO, OpenAIRE, OASPA, OSF.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

- A Open Science and Open Education Committee will act as a monitoring instance;
- Integrating open practices into incentives and assessment practices in E³UDRES²;
- Establishing key performance indicators (KPIs) for open science and education.

1.5 Engaging Citizens and Society

Policy:

As European University Alliance committed to smart and sustainable regional development, engaging citizens and society is at the heart of the E³UDRES² mission. Our goal is to empower citizens as co-creators of knowledge and solutions, ensuring that research and innovation directly address real-world needs. We promote inclusive decision-making processes where citizens also help shape policy, fostering stronger democracies and just outcomes for all. The term “citizens” refers to individuals, while “society” includes a group of people or the community of people.

Engaging with citizens and society is based on four key pillars:

- **Science Communication & Dissemination:**

E³UDRES² communicates its scientific activities in target group-orientated language to raise awareness for scientific questions and solutions, to higher the visibility of E³UDRES² and its scientific activities and to contribute to the overall E³UDRES² claim as engaged university. Science Communication also supports the growth of the E³UDRES² and innovation network.

- **Citizen Science:**

Citizens are active participants in the scientific process. By involving them in the development of research questions, target-group orientated issues are addressed. Citizens can contribute to the collection of data by embedding themselves in the research field. By involving them in the analysis of data and the development of prototypes, scientific solutions can be developed directly for and with users. E³UDRES² Science Outreach activities contribute to 1) overcoming scientific scepticism 2) enabling citizen participation in the research process and to 3) a better fit of scientific solutions for users, to speed up the innovation process and make a real impact for society.

- **Science and technology transfer:**

Science and technology transfer activities translate research into practice and make research outcomes more readily available to industry and society. E³UDRES² promotes open access of research results wherever legally feasible. Dedicated transfer units at the E³UDRES² partner institutions and when possible joint ones coordinate and support the efforts, also providing contact points to transfer professionals from other HEIs and from companies.

- **Democratic Research & Policy-Making:**

We foster mechanisms through which citizens can influence research agendas and policy discussions, enabling more responsive, fair, participative and community-driven approaches. This creates a virtuous cycle: better policies, greater legitimacy, and more effective regional development, as well as smoother integration of new solutions in all societal practices (e.g. in social care and health systems).

E³UDRES² research and innovation activities benefit from integrating citizen science engagement by:

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- Improving data quality and relevance through crowdsourced feedback and participation;
- Identifying new emerging trends and societal needs;
- Empowering citizens to co-create solutions that are both innovative and actionable;
- Building public trust and improving ethical considerations. (democratic research and policy-making); open access to the research process, findings and data promotes a sense of ownership and equity;
- Strengthening the connections between knowledge institutions and local communities (with local government and public authorities, companies) as stakeholders;
- Ensuring that research addresses real-world challenges with community-driven solutions; research and priority setting can be driven by the community;
- Increasing science literacy: citizens learn about the different stages in the research process.

By bridging the gap between science and society, it enables non-experts to actively participate in research, making scientific processes more transparent, accessible, and relevant. Moreover, citizen science drives innovation by connecting researchers with communities to co-create solutions tailored to societal needs. It also promotes lifelong learning, empowering individuals—including those from vulnerable groups—with new skills, curiosity, and critical thinking. Importantly, the data and insights generated through citizen science can inform better policy decisions in areas like environment, health, and urban development. In essence, citizen science is a powerful tool for achieving more just, informed, and sustainable societies. By making science more inclusive, collaborative, and actionable, we are shaping the future of research—one that is deeply connected to the needs and aspirations of the communities we serve.

Support and Infrastructure:

To truly integrate citizens into our research and innovation processes, E³UDRES² invests in robust support mechanisms:

- Crowdsourcing & Citizen Science Platforms;
- Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) / Citizen Science;
- Technology;
- Legal & ethical frameworks Ensuring fairness, data protection, and inclusive participation;
- Training and capacity development.

The Maturity Model with Engagement Competences and incompetence's based on EURAXESS profile descriptors supports the planning, communication, understanding context, networking & outreach, transdisciplinary teamwork, training, consulting and education, stakeholder-/citizen incentives & motivation, and ethical considerations for citizen science activities.

Governance:

E³UDRES² governance prioritizes community needs and democratic engagement. An E³UDRES² Citizen & Stakeholder Advisory Board will provide early and ongoing input on research directions and policy priorities. This ensures alignment with the lived realities and expectations of regional populations.

This advisory structure ensures that activities are aligned with the real-life experiences, needs, and values of regional populations. In doing so, we embed social justice, inclusiveness, and responsiveness into institutional decision-making and help ensure that research outcomes are meaningful and actionable for society.

Collaboration and partnerships:

We build on the strength of regional innovation hubs and engage in strategic partnerships to anchor citizen science deeply in our ecosystems. Collaboration with networks such as the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and similar platforms facilitates knowledge sharing, harmonization of practices, and international visibility. At the local level, partnerships with municipal governments, SMEs, NGOs e.g. civil, schools, and community groups enable research to be grounded in place-based realities. These relationships foster mutual trust, sustained engagement, and co-ownership of innovation outcomes, ensuring that solutions are regionally relevant, inclusive, and scalable.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

We will implement inclusive, participatory, and transparent monitoring frameworks that go beyond basic metrics. Our approach will assess:

- Citizen engagement levels (breadth, depth, and continuity of participation);
- Impact on real-world challenges and contributions to policy change;
- Social equity outcomes, including representation of marginalized groups;
- Growth in science literacy, critical thinking, and trust in research.

To ensure continuous improvement and community accountability, we will use participatory evaluation tools such as citizen panels, storytelling, open data dashboards, and iterative feedback loops. These methods allow citizens to play an active role in shaping how success is defined, measured, and communicated.

1.6 Human Resources

Policy:

The E³UDRES² alliance recognizes the importance of its people and talents and therefore supports personnel development of its staff in the field of research and research management, as well as other administrative areas supporting research and researchers. The E³UDRES² alliance commits itself to the principles of the European Charter for Researchers. All E³UDRES² partners aim to achieve and maintain the HR Excellence in Research Award.

The E³UDRES² Human Resources Policy is based on the core principles of the European Charter for Researchers:

- Ethics, Integrity, Gender and Open Science;
- Researchers' Assessment, Recruitment and Progression;
- Working Conditions and Practices;
- Research Careers and Talent Development.

E³UDRES² will support human resources in research with:

- **Career advice and development**

The academic world is still characterised by precarious working conditions (especially with regard to fixed-term contracts, insecure future planning, etc.). E³UDRES² supports the development of alliance wide flexible careers models for researchers, academic and administrative staff to offer more secure research careers.

- **Training & professional development**

Capacity building activities shall support the professional development of the E³UDRES² staff involved in research and research management. E³UDRES² will provide targeted training opportunities and will use successful training programmes of the E³UDRES² partner institutions to open it for a wider community.

- **International mobility & collaboration**

E³UDRES² offers a strong network for international collaboration including higher education institutions and numerous associated partners. E³UDRES² further aims to connect with research relevant networks and stakeholders (e.g. European Open Science Cloud) to open up new opportunities for collaboration. E³UDRES² promotes international mobility opportunities.

- **Open, transparent & merit-based recruitment**

The E³UDRES² alliance commits itself to implement open, transparent and merit-based recruiting systems, starting with all jobs in research and research management directly linked to the E³UDRES² alliance activities and expanded to all jobs within the E³UDRES² alliance.

- **Diversity & gender equality**

Diversity and gender equality is a core element in supporting human resources within the E³UDRES² alliance. Those principles should be applied on all levels (diversity and gender equality in research teams, diversity and gender equality in the content of research and innovation). The E³UDRES² alliance offers awareness activities, trainings and will integrate aspects in the recruiting of staff.

- **Ethics & integrity**

The E³UDRES² alliance promotes scientific integrity and awareness of ethical aspects in research. This is a crucial element in the quality assurance of the E³UDRES² research activities. E³UDRES² shall discuss the implementation of a E³UDRES² Ethical Advisory Board or use the already implemented activities in the E³UDRES² institutions for ethical advice.

The E³UDRES² alliance is supporting the Ent-r-e-novators model which integrates entrepreneurship, research, and innovation and supporting researchers in translating their work into societal impact. Knowing that academics cannot fulfil all task equally, the aim is to raise awareness of how research results can be translated to business, innovation and impact.

Support and Infrastructure:

Promoting mobility within the alliance, where knowledge sharing takes place, including mobility between 1) different roles, 2) different work tasks and their diversity, 3) between institutions is a key element of HR support.

The alliance will develop policies that promote equity in academic career paths, including structured career progression frameworks, mentorship programs, and incentives for interdisciplinary research. Promoting open-access policies and ensuring equal representation of underrepresented groups in leadership roles can also foster inclusivity.

The alliance will strive to offer long-term career stability, access to suitable research infrastructure, and funding opportunities. Participation in European funding programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) and adherence to the principles of the European Charter for Researchers can enhance the alliance's attractiveness.

The joint E³UDRES² HR policy, fosters attractive working conditions by:

- Implementing flexible working policies;
- Enhancing research infrastructure;
- Standardizing OTM-R recruitment across institutions;
- Providing structured career progression pathways.

The joint E³UDRES² HR strategy includes the following activities, that could attribute to supporting academic careers fostering innovative approaches in R&I:

- Cross-institutional career development plans;
- Interdisciplinary training programs;
- Centralized repository for research training materials.

Stability in research careers can be ensured by creating clear career pathways, reducing reliance on short-term contracts, in accordance with national legislation, and integrating research with teaching and knowledge transfer activities. Institutional support for early-career researchers and continuous professional development is important.

By establishing structured career models, introducing mentoring programs, and ensuring transparent recruitment, as well as mobility incentives and career development support Joint HRS4R will strengthen researcher retention within the alliance.

Governance:

A joint support unit related to capacity building within the E³UDRES² alliance will support the governance of career development initiatives of E³UDRES².

Collaboration and partnerships:

E³UDRES² promotes collaboration within the alliance by setting up joint doctoral programmes, mentorship initiatives and mobility schemes among partner institutions to support academic careers fostering innovative approaches in R&I.

Joint PhD programs should incorporate interdisciplinary approaches, allowing candidates to work across institutions while benefiting from shared expertise.

The research strategy should accommodate institutional differences by adopting flexible policies that recognise diverse research career models. The newly developed Joint HRS4R promotes a flexible and adaptable approach, allowing institutions to tailor actions to their specific legal and structural contexts. The strategy emphasises:

- Aligning career models while respecting institutional autonomy;
- Ensuring equitable access to training, mobility, and professional development regardless of institutional differences.

The E³UDRES² open innovation hubs and E³UDRES² Centres of Excellence will act as platform for peer-learning and setting up partnerships with external stakeholders. This will support the promotion of interdisciplinary research opportunities.

The Centres of Excellence focus on key strategic research areas and provide infrastructure for collaborative research for all levels of researchers. They should act as hubs for advanced training and collaboration, ensuring:

- High-quality research training;
- Promote opportunities for international mobility;
- Promoting career development for all levels of researchers;
- Bridging academia and industry for innovation.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

The HRS4R process itself as well as the regular re-evaluation is a key tool for monitoring and evaluating the joint E³UDRES² human resource strategy. As all E³UDRES² founding partners are expected to achieve the HRS4R label, the initial application.

1.7 Research and Innovation ecosystems

Policy:

The E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem aims to be a dynamic and self-sustaining ecosystem where education, research, (local) government, citizens, NGOs and business seamlessly collaborate. This model is based on principles of organic growth, open knowledge, infrastructure sharing, and democratic decision-making. The E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem functions as a living network where different partners work together to drive innovation and societal impact. It encompasses from internal ecosystem of each E³UDRES² partnering organization, consisting of its organizational units, organizational culture, processes and teamwork, as well as external ecosystem – the partnerships important for the existence of partnering university, region they represent and the consortium as such.

The E³UDRES² alliance is a resilient, adaptive ecosystem where universities interact with regional and national actors, respond to European priorities, and evolve through challenge-based research. Just like a healthy natural ecosystem, it thrives on diversity, interconnectedness, and continuous learning.

In this living system, E³UDRES² researchers, educators and professors, as well as students strive as the primary producers from the academic perspective, generating new knowledge, methods, and solutions that address real-world challenges. This knowledge is inspired by, developed with, taken up and applied by local companies, public institutions, NGOs, and schools – our ecosystem's consumers – who help shape, test, and scale our innovations in real-life contexts.

The regional environments in which E³UDRES² partners are embedded provide the essential habitat that grounds E³UDRES² mission. The alliance campuses are more than addresses – they are ecosystems in themselves, offering unique challenges and opportunities that define the direction and relevance of the work.

Knowledge transfer units, innovation offices, and intermediaries function as pollinators, ensuring that ideas, expertise, and practices are exchanged across disciplines, sectors, and borders. Meanwhile, evaluation and quality assurance teams act as decomposers, transforming past experiences – both successes and failures – into fertile ground for new growth.

Funding programmes, shared infrastructure and digital resources form the vital nutrients and water that sustain the ecosystem, while societal needs and European policy priorities act as the sunlight, energizing and directing efforts toward mission-oriented research and innovation.

The E³UDRES² ecosystem thrives through collaboration with regional stakeholders, co-creating solutions to shared challenges in education, sustainability, digitalisation, and social inclusion. It is enriching biodiversity, with multidisciplinary approaches and diverse partnerships enhancing resilience, creativity, and adaptability.

Through this integrated ecosystem, E³UDRES² responds to change by co-creating it. E³UDRES² research and innovation ecosystems function to regenerate our regions, influence European policy, and empower people and communities by making research more inclusive, applied, and impact-driven.

Support and Infrastructure:

Digital platforms as well as networking events support the setting up and administration of the ecosystem.

Governance:

Governance within the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem is built on sociocratic principles—focusing on consent, transparency, and continuous feedback. This method ensures inclusive decision-making and strengthens the legitimacy and trust within the ecosystem.

Collaboration and partnerships:

The E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem involves the E³UDRES² members, associated partners, international networks, regional and local networks as well as stakeholders from business, society and policy makers.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

An overarching Steering Board provides governance, ensures strategic direction, and aligns the ecosystem's goals with broader policies and institutional priorities.

The Board includes the responsible individuals (e.g., senior leaders or presidents) from each university involved in the ecosystem, ensuring that institutional perspectives and priorities are fully represented in the governance process. These individuals ensure alignment between the ecosystem's objectives and the broader institutional strategies, fostering collaboration at both the local and network-wide levels.

The regular evaluation of the impact of the E³UDRES² alliance to the regions will support the further development of the R&I ecosystem.

2. Action Plan

The Action Plan of WP2 focusses on the actions identified in the research and innovation agenda related to the chapter on future oriented agenda.

The recommendations elaborated in the action plan are addressed to different stakeholders within the E³UDRES² European University Alliance.

- *E³UDRES² association*: The E³UDRES² association, registered under Austrian Law, is the umbrella organisation of the E³UDRES² Alliance supporting the implementation and further development of the common vision, mission and strategy of the European University Alliance E³UDRES². The work of the association is not tied to any third-party funding.
- *E³UDRES² alliance*: The E³UDRES² alliance, as commitment of 9 higher education partners with a joint developed mission for the next years. This agenda serves as guiding document for the development of further projects in research and innovation.
- *E³UDRES² 2.0*: E³UDRES² 2.0 is the core project supporting the implementation of the E³UDRES² European University Alliance. The funding is confirmed until September 2027.
- *E³UDRES² satellite projects*: The E³UDRES² alliance has already been successful in acquiring additional research and innovation projects. Those project teams shall also be aware of the agenda and try to synchronize wherever possible their activities with the goals of the research and innovation agenda.

The following actions are recommended by WP2 to successfully and sustainably implement the joint research and innovation agenda:

2.1 Communication of the R&I Agenda to researchers, staff, etc.

Achieving the goals of the agenda requires the commitment of everyone. To make this possible, the agenda must be communicated accordingly. This can be done via:

- Publication of the agenda on the website (www.entrenovators.eu + www.eudres.eu);
- E³UDRES² newsletter;
- Presentation at E³UDRES² meetings (e.g. General Assembly Poster Session, Executive Board, WP4 E³UDRES²);
- Targeted approach of key multipliers (e.g.: heads of Centre of Excellences, E³UDRES² Scientific Council, members of WP4 E³UDRES² 2.0);
- Kick-off event where the plan is presented to the entire E³UDRES² community (e.g. E³UDRES² update);
- Use video and/or podcast to explain the agenda.

Also, the agenda should be easy to find. For greater visibility, it can be made available in the E³UDRES² Arena, the E³UDRES² online platform (<https://arena.eudres.eu/>).

2.2 Set up an evaluation and monitoring structure for R&I Agenda

The monitoring and evaluation concept of the joint research and innovation agenda is based on the following pillars:

- a) regular monitoring of the relevance of the activities and impact for the region (WP8 in E³UDRES² monitoring tool impact) according to the E³UDRES² focus areas:
 - Health, Wellbeing and Social Inclusion for Regions;
 - Digital Solutions and (Applied) Deep Tech for Regions;
 - Resilient Economy and Innovation for Regions;
 - Creative Industries for Region's Identity;
- b) actively contribute to CoARA and make use of those developments for further elaboration of the evaluation and monitoring concept;
- c) monitoring the implementation of the agenda itself.

Ad a) It is recommended to include internal and external stakeholders in the monitoring and evaluation concept. Therefore, the E³UDRES² Scientific Council (internal perspective) and E³UDRES² Advisory Board (external perspective) shall be asked to act as evaluation boards. The evaluation shall take place on an annual basis and can for example be integrated in the E³UDRES² General Assembly Meeting. Quantitative key performance indicators (e.g. number of project applications and number of funded projects in the relevant focus areas, number of external partners involved in the research and innovation activities, number of publications) shall be combined with qualitative indicators to get an overall perspective of the research and innovation activities within the E³UDRES² alliance. The evaluation and monitoring concept shall be efficient and focused on the core objectives of the agenda. It should consider the fact that E³UDRES² mainly represents universities of applied sciences with a strong collaborative and mission-oriented approach. There is a strong link to the quality management and evaluation of E³UDRES² which is currently located within WP8 of E³UDRES² 2.0. In case of the set up of a quality management independent from the project structure, this task shall be delegated to this quality management group. In addition to that, there shall be a tight link to the regional engagement assessment concept, which is currently developed under WP8.

Ad b) As some E³UDRES² members are already actively contributing to the discussions within the CoARA network, the results of those discussions shall be integrated in an innovative evaluation and monitoring concept for the research activities within E³UDRES². To guarantee the knowledge transfer within E³UDRES² it is recommended that all members who are already actively contributing to CoARA shall meet regularly to share their ideas. Those members, who have not signed the CoARA declaration yet, shall be motivated to do so.

Ad c) Delegate the decision on the group/board/WP who will monitor the implementation of the agenda. The suggestion is to link it to WP4 of E³UDRES² 2.0 and the E³UDRES² association. In case a joint research centre is set up, this task can be delegated to this centre.

2.3 Recommendation for further discussion in the decision making bodies of E³UDRES²

(E³UDRES² Executive Board and E³UDRES² Association Managing Board)

- *Incentive mechanisms* such as conferences, innovation calls and awards of excellence help develop new creative, interdisciplinary ideas and approaches for research and innovation inside the alliance and with its partners and stakeholders. An important decision needs to be made related to the funding and organisation of this mechanisms, especially in the context of the further development of the E³UDRES² association.
- *Joint research support units*, to be drafted and installed in the broader alliance context, will support researchers and innovators to identify potential calls for their innovative ideas to develop targeted funding applications and expand their cooperation networks.

2.4 Recommendation for further discussion in other WPs and projects

- *E³UDRES² 2.0 WP7*
Training, like e.g. proposal writing, project management etc. accompany the personal growth of the *individual actors in the research process to succeed in competitive award procedures and are progressively included in more comprehensive training programmes and joint activities.* -> *capacity work package E³UDRES²*
- *E³UDRES² 2.0 WP9*
Set up virtual networking opportunities as alternative for the previous wonder.me tool in the E³UDRES² arena
- *E³UDRES² 2.0 WP10*
Networking events ensure broader collaboration. These gatherings help expand the pool of engaged individuals inside and outside the partner institutions by creating more points of contact and fostering familiarity among a wider range of contributors. Since people tend to collaborate with those they know, increasing the number of personal connections is key to involving more individuals and boosting the overall capacity of the project. It is highly recommended to set up different ways of virtual networking. Virtual opportunities for networking shall be also included in the E³UDRES² arena.

The communication and dissemination team of the E³UDRES² alliance, currently part of WP10 of E³UDRES² 2.0 can be a driver for those networking events.

3. Annex

The Annex provides the approval letters of the Research and Innovation Agenda (chapter 1 of this document) of the participating institutions in the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project.

E³UDRES Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan

Institutional Approval Confirmation

We, the undersigned, representing Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal, hereby confirm that the approach, objectives, scope and content of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan* have been officially reviewed and approved by our institution in accordance with our internal governance procedures.

This confirmation serves as a formal proof of institutional endorsement and support for the Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan as part of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators* international collaboration, in accordance with the project's Grant Agreement.

Signed on behalf of:

Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal

Assinado por: **ÂNGELA MARIA GOMES TELES DE MATOS CREMON DE LEMOS**
Num. de Identificação: 08339063
Data: 2025.07.26 16:47:02+01'00'

[Angela Lemos, President of Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal]

Date: 28.07.2025

Place: Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal, Portugal

E³UDRES Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan

Institutional Approval Confirmation

We, the undersigned, representing Fachhochschule St. Pölten GmbH, hereby confirm that the approach, objectives, scope and content of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan* have been officially reviewed and approved by our institution in accordance with our internal governance procedures.

This confirmation serves, in accordance with the project's Grant Agreement, as a formal proof of institutional endorsement and support for the Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan as part of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators* international collaboration.

Signed on behalf of:

Fachhochschule St. Pölten GmbH

Campus-Platz 1

A-3100 St. Pölten

FH-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Johann Haag

ST. PÖLTEN UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

Fachhochschule St. Pölten GmbH
Campus-Platz 1, 3100 St. Pölten, Austria

T: +43 2742 313 228
FN 146616m LG St. Pölten
DVR 1028669F

FH-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Hannes Raffaseder

Date: 31.07.2025

Place: St. Pölten, Austria

E³UDRES Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan

Institutional Approval Confirmation

We, the undersigned, representing **UC Limburg vzw**, hereby confirm that the approach, objectives, scope and content of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan* have been officially reviewed and approved by our institution in accordance with our internal governance procedures.

This confirmation serves, in accordance with the project's Grant Agreement, as a formal proof of institutional endorsement and support for the Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan as part of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators* international collaboration.

Signed on behalf of:

UC Limburg, Board of Directors

Marc Vandewalle
(Signature)

Digitaal ondertekend door
Marc Vandewalle (Signature)
Datum: 2025.08.22 14:53:03
+02'00'

Marc Vandewalle, President

Date: 22/8/2025

Place: Diepenbeek

E³UDRES² Common R&I Agenda

Institutional Approval Confirmation

We, the undersigned, representing Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT), hereby confirm that the approach, objectives, scope and content of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Common R&I Agenda* have been officially reviewed and approved by our institution in accordance with our internal governance procedures.

This confirmation serves, in accordance with the project's Grant Agreement, as a formal proof of institutional endorsement and support for the Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan as part of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators* international collaboration.

Signed on behalf of:

Politehnica University of Timisoara

Assoc.prof.dr.eng. Florin DRĂGAN

Rector

Date: 04.09.2025

Place: Timișoara

IZRAKSTS

Vidzemes Augstskolas Senāta sēdes PROTOKOLS Valmierā

Nr.6

2025.gada 27.augustā

Sēdi vada: *Senāta priekšsēdētājs* Oskars Java,

Protokolē: *Senāta sekretāre* Evija Lubņevska,

Sēdes dalībnieki:

senatori:

1. *Dr.phil., rektore* Agnese Dāvidsone,
 2. *Mg.geogr., SZF lektors* Ilgvars Ābols,
 3. *Mg.sc.pol., ViAZI zinātniskā asistente* Anna Broka,
 4. *Dr.sc.ing., IF asociētais profesors* Arnis Cīrulis,
 5. *Dr.math., IF docente* Aija Cunska,
 6. *Mg.sc.ing., ViAZI zinātniskais asistents* Kristaps Felzenbergs,
 7. *Dr.sc.ing., ViAZI pētnieks* Oskars Java,
 8. *Dr.paed., ViAZI pētniece* Anžela Jurāne–Brēmane,
 9. *Mg.sc.soc., SZF lektore* Liene Ločmele,
 10. *Dr.sc.ing., ViAZI vadošais pētnieks* Kaspars Osis,
 11. *Dr.hist., ViAZI pētnieks* Jānis Šiliņš,
 12. *Dr.oec., SZF lektore* Ieva Zaumane
 13. *Bakalaura studiju prog. "Informācijas Tehnoloģijas" 3.k. studente* Ligija Līva Vītoliņa
 14. *Bakalaura studiju prog. "Komunikācija un sabiedriskās attiecības" 4.k. students* Ēriks Ralfs Blauberģs
- pārējie dalībnieki –**
1. *ViAZI vadošais pētnieks, ViA Padomes loceklis* Gatis Krūmiņš,
 2. *SZF lektore, zinātniskā sekretāre* Zane Kudure,

Sēde noris MS Teams

Sēdes sākums 2025.gada 27.augustā, plkst.8.30

Sēdes beigas 2025.gada 27.augustā, plkst.9.00

Darba kārtība

1. Par *E³UDRES² common R&I agenda and action plan (E³UDRES² vienotā pētniecības un attīstības darba kārtības un rīcības plāna) saskaņošanu Vidzemes Augstskolā (O.Java)*

1.

Par E³UDRES² common R&I agenda and action plan (E³UDRES² vienotā pētniecības un attīstības darba kārtības un rīcības plāna) saskaņošanu Vidzemes Augstskolā

O.Java informē:

E³UDRES² vienotā pētniecības un attīstības darba kārtības un rīcības plāns tapis, projekta *Ent-r-e-novators* WP2 "Pētniecības un inovāciju stratēģija" darba pakā iesaistītajam personālam sadarbojoties ar pārējās projekta darba pakās iesaistīto personālu, projekta *E³UDRES² 1.0* pētniekiem un studējošajiem (sanāksmes, fokusgrupas intervijas, aptaujas). Vienotā pētniecības un attīstības darba kārtība un rīcības plāns ir izstrādāts kā instruments, lai palīdzētu projekta *E³UDRES²* konsorcijs partneriem ciešāk sadarboties. Pirms šo dokumentu iesniegt kā nodevumu Eiropas Komisijai, nepieciešams *E³UDRES² 1.0* partnerinstitūciju saskaņojums, ViA gadījumā – Senāta.

[..]

Balsojums par E³UDRES² common R&I agenda and action plan (E³UDRES² vienotā pētniecības un attīstības darba kārtības un rīcības plāna) saskaņošanu Vidzemes Augstskolā

[..]

par – 13; pret – 0, atturas – 1

Lēmums Nr.2025/6/1.1

Apstiprināt E³UDRES² common R&I agenda and action plan (E³UDRES² vienotā pētniecības un attīstības darba kārtības un rīcības plānu).

[..]

Senāta priekšsēdētājs

Oskars Java

IZRAKSTS PAREIZS
Vidzemes Augstskolas Senāta sekretāre
Valmierā, 17.09.2025.

E.Lubņevska

E³UDRES Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan

Institutional Approval Confirmation

I, the undersigned Dr. Csaba Gyuricza rector, representing the **Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences** (seat: H-2100 Gödöllő, Páter Károly utca 1., Hungary, institutional code: FI51129, group identification number: 17784227-5-44, VAT number: 19294784-4-44, EU VAT number: HU17784227), hereby confirm that the approach, objectives, scope and content of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan* have been officially reviewed and approved by our institution in accordance with our internal governance procedures.

This confirmation serves, in accordance with the project's Grant Agreement, as a formal proof of institutional endorsement and support for the Common R&I Agenda and Action Plan as part of the *E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators* international collaboration.

Signed on behalf of:

Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences

Dr. Csaba Gyuricza, rector

Date: August 2025

Place: Gödöllő, Hungary

E³UDRES²
**ent.r.e.
novators**
ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

Funded by
the European Union

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